

Defluoridation of wastewater using copper oxide incorporated alumina

Mrunal Mahajan, Nitin Labhsetwar, Sadhana Rayalu and Amit Bansiwala*

Environmental Materials Division, CSIR-National Environmental Engineering Research Institute (CSIR-NEERI),
Nehru Marg, Nagpur-440 020, Maharashtra, India

E-mail : ak_bansiwala@neeri.res.in

Abstract : Contamination of water with fluoride is an important issue from environmental point of view, which is also imposing threats to human health from several decades. In addition to geogenic sources of fluoride, industrial wastewater also contributes significantly towards fluoride pollution. The present study deals with removal of fluoride from simulated wastewater using modified alumina as an adsorbent. The adsorbent namely copper oxide coated alumina (COCA) was synthesized by impregnation method. Granular activated alumina beads were impregnated with copper sulfate solution, which was then calcined in presence of air. The material thus prepared has been characterized using powder XRD. It has been studied for fluoride uptake properties in simulated wastewater containing fluoride as well as other co-anions in higher concentrations, commonly present in industrial discharge. The material shows an adsorption capacity of 7.3 mg g⁻¹, from an initial concentration of 51.8 mg L⁻¹, with no significant change in pH as well as no release of copper and aluminium. This material was earlier investigated for defluoridation of drinking water and also shows potential for its application in fluoride removal from wastewater.

Keywords : Defluoridation, wastewater, copper oxide, granular alumina.

Introduction

Fluorides are found in relative abundance in our daily lives, commonly in drinking water, either added artificially as a dental aid or is naturally occurring in many areas of the country. Some toothpastes are sold with sodium fluoride (NaF) added as a dental aid¹. However, excess fluoride intake, besides affecting the dental and skeletal system, shows adverse health effects on muscle fiber degeneration, low hemoglobin level, deformities in RBCs, excessive thirst, gastrointestinal discomfort, etc.². Some reports claim that fluoride may interfere with DNA synthesis³, carbohydrates, lipids, proteins, vitamins and mineral metabolism. Fluoride toxicity may occur by several ways. Ingested fluoride acts on the intestinal mucosa; it can later form hydrofluoric acid in the stomach, which leads to gastro-intestinal irritation or corrosive effects⁴. Fluoride can also interfere with a number of enzymes disrupting oxidative phosphorylation, glycolysis, coagulation, and neurotransmission.

Fluoride is used abundantly in industry. High fluoride level in wastewater is major environmental problem for industries using hydrofluoric acid such as semiconductor, aluminium process, solar cell or metals manufactur-

ing industries, or as a reactant or catalyst in the plastics, pharmaceutical, petroleum refining, refrigeration industries etc. Fluoride concentrations in the effluents from these industries may range from 10 to more than 10,000 mg L⁻¹ in rinse waters, however, as per BIS : 10500, the discharge norm for disposal in land or surface water is up to 15 mg L⁻¹. Therefore, on site treatment is essential to support manufacturing facilities to meet their environmental obligations⁵. Keeping in view the adverse effects of fluoride on human health; there is an urgent need to find out an effective way for the removal of excess fluoride from industrial wastewater. The traditional method of removing fluoride by precipitation and coagulation processes with iron(III)⁶, activated alumina⁷, alum sludge⁸ and calcium⁹ have been widely investigated. In addition, ion exchange¹⁰⁻¹⁴, reverse osmosis^{15,16} and electro dialysis¹⁷ have also been studied for the removal of excess amounts of fluoride from wastewater. However, the demerits of most of the above methods are high maintenance and operational costs, secondary pollution (generation of toxic sludge, etc.) and complicated procedure involved in the treatment. A review on sustainable technologies for the defluoridation of drinking water has been

made by Ayoob *et al.*¹⁸, in which different technologies are compared and the strengths and limitations of different methods used for defluoridation, are discussed. Among various removal methods, adsorption is found to be the most promising method, which can be used in large scale by many water treatment plants besides being efficient and cost effective.

Activated alumina, which is usually available in the form of granular aluminium oxide (Al_2O_3) with high internal surface area of about 200 to 300 $\text{m}^2 \text{g}^{-1}$, possess high fluoride adsorption capacity depending on its crystalline phase as well as surface functional groups. However, the adsorption properties of activated alumina are affected to an extent, by the presence of co-anions in wastewater and maximum fluoride removal capacity is generally realized only under acidic pH, below 6. There is also a possibility of leaching of aluminium in treated water at this lower pH in certain alumina, especially under poor control over pH, which is the case for wastewater. To overcome above limitations, various chemical modifications of activated alumina have been suggested. Alum impregnated activated alumina as an adsorbent for defluoridation of drinking water was suggested by Tripathi *et al.*¹⁹. In one of our previous communication²⁰, we have reported copper oxide impregnated activated alumina, which posse high fluoride uptake capacity for drinking water treatment in presence of various co-ions and in wide pH range.

The objective of the present study is to investigate the efficiency of copper oxide impregnated activated alumina (COCA) for removal of fluoride from wastewater. The adsorbent was synthesized and evaluated for its fluoride uptake in industrial wastewater. To determine adsorption and kinetic parameters, batch adsorption studies were performed. Also, batch adsorption data was generated that gave the effect of different anions commonly encountered in wastewater, on defluoridation using COCA.

Materials and methods :

Materials :

Granular activated alumina (PURALOX) was provided by SASOL, GmbH, Germany. It was a high purity gamma alumina with pore size in the range of 50–200 Å. The alumina was in the form of spherical beads and was used as such after washing with deionised water (DIW) (18

MX resistivity, obtained from MilliQDI water system). Copper sulfate, sodium fluoride, sodium chloride, sodium sulfate, sodium carbonate, sodium bicarbonate used, was purchased from E. Merck India Ltd. A stock solution of 1000 mg L^{-1} fluoride was prepared by dissolving 2.2111 g salt of sodium fluoride in 1000 mL of DI water and working solution was prepared freshly by appropriate dilution of stock solution by DI water. All chemicals used in this study were of analytical grade.

Synthesis of adsorbent :

Ten gram of activated alumina granules were taken and washed with DI water. After drying for 3 h at 110 °C in oven, it was kept in orbital shaking incubator with different concentrations of copper sulfate solution ranging from 0.001 M to 0.05 M for 24 h. Then the material was filtered and residue was washed with DI water to remove excess copper sulfate. The washed material was air dried for 8 h and then calcined in presence of air at 500 °C for 4 h. These materials with different impregnation concentration were screened for fluoride removal efficiency. Best fluoride removal efficiency was found for alumina impregnated with 0.005 M CuSO_4 , without any effect on pH and aluminium release in treated water. Thus, it was subsequently used as an adsorbent.

Characterization :

The synthesized COCA was characterized using X-ray diffractometer (Model Phillips : PW-1830). The operating target voltage was 35 kV and the current was 20 mA. The radiations of Cu $\text{K}\alpha$ were generated using X-ray generator model (PW 1729) of same make and the β radiations were filtered using monochromator. The sample was powdered and scanned for 2θ ranges from 10° to 110°.

Fluoride adsorption study :

100 mL of 51.8 mg L^{-1} fluoride solution was taken into a PVC conical flask and known weight of adsorbent was added and kept for shaking on a Rotary shaker (Model No. CIS-24, Remi Instruments Mumbai, India) in order to attain the equilibrium. The solution was filtered using Whatman filter paper No. 42 and the fluoride analysis was done by ion selective electrode method using ion meter (Thermoelectron, USA, Model 920A) coupled with fluoride ion selective electrode (Thermoelectron USA, Model 9609BNWP). TISAB III was used as buffer for maintaining the pH and background ion concentrations

during measurement. pH was measured using the same ion meter coupled with pH electrode (Orion 9490). All adsorption experiments were performed at room temperature ($25\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C} \pm 2\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$). Batch adsorption experiments were carried out to determine the effect of different parameters such as adsorbent dose, initial fluoride concentration, and co-existing ions. The adsorption capacity for fluoride removal was calculated by following expression :

$$q_e = (C_i - C_e) * V / (W * 1000)$$

where q_e is the adsorption amount (mg g^{-1}) at equilibrium, C_i and C_e are the initial and equilibrium concentrations of fluoride (mg L^{-1}) respectively, V is the volume (mL) of the aqueous solution and W is the mass (g) of adsorbent used to carry out the experiments.

Leaching of Al and other heavy metals (as impurity) from adsorbent were also determined by using Inductively Coupled Plasma-Atomic Emission Spectroscopy (ICP-AES, Model OPTIMA 4100DV). Experiments were repeated twice for better accuracy and blank experiments were also performed during the study. Same experimental procedure was followed to study the effect of pH, initial fluoride concentration and co-existing ions, etc. on adsorption of fluoride on COCA.

Results and discussion

Characterization of adsorbent :

The BET surface area of copper oxide coated alumina was found to be $189.25\text{ m}^2\text{ g}^{-1}$ ²⁰. The XRD patterns of bare activated alumina and modified alumina remains almost same, indicating that the typical structure of alumina was retained after copper oxide coating and peaks at 2θ values of about 45° , 35° and 61° in both, confirms presence of gamma alumina phases. Also the XRD patterns of COCA before and after treatment with fluoride ions shows no significant changes, shown in Fig. 1, indicating no phase change of the adsorbent on adsorption of fluoride.

Effect of adsorbent dose :

The effect of adsorbent dose on removal of fluoride using COCA is shown in the Fig. 2, in which percent fluoride removal and fluoride uptake (mg g^{-1}) are plotted against adsorbent dose (initial pH 7.6 and contact time of 2 h). It was observed that percentage removal of fluoride increased with the increase in adsorbent dose while loading capacity gradually decreased for the same, which may be due to low concentration of fluoride available at higher adsorbent dose. It was observed that percent fluoride re-

Fig. 1. X-Ray diffraction pattern of unmodified alumina and COCA before and after defluoridation.

Fig. 2. Effect of adsorbent dose on % fluoride removal and adsorption capacity for COCA.

removal increased from 27.4% to 83.6% with increase in COCA dose from 1 to 10 g L⁻¹ at initial concentration of 51.8 mg L⁻¹. This is due to the increase in the active sites/fluoride ratio. In the present study, the permissible limit of 15 mg L⁻¹ of fluoride for wastewater discharge as per Indian Standards (BIS : 10500) was attained at dose of 7 g L⁻¹. However, 20 mg L⁻¹ was achieved at dose of 4 g L⁻¹, giving capacity of 7.3 mg g⁻¹. This can be further diluted to attain desirable limits. Hence, a dose of 4 g L⁻¹ was considered as optimal for further studies.

Effect of the presence of co-existing ions :

The industrial wastewater contaminated with fluoride usually contains other ions, which may compete with fluoride during adsorption process. Hence, it is necessary to study the effect of co-existing ions on the removal of fluoride. The adsorption studies were performed in simulated wastewater prepared from DI water containing Cl⁻ (100 mg L⁻¹), SO₄²⁻ (300 mg L⁻¹), HCO₃⁻ (200 mg L⁻¹) and CO₃²⁻ (200 mg L⁻¹) ions, by keeping initial concentration of fluoride as 50 g L⁻¹, at temperature 25 °C ± 2 °C, with shaking speed of 150 rpm and contact time 2 h, pH being in range of 9.1 to 9.5. The effect of co-ions on the fluoride removal efficiency is shown in the Fig. 3. It shows decrease in the fluoride removal efficiency to the tune of 15-20%, which may be due to competition for the adsorption sites and also due to increase in initial

pH of the solution (pH 9.1). However, the adsorbent still shows reasonably high fluoride uptake in presence of several fold higher concentrations of co-ions, thus suggesting its fluoride selectivity and potential for wastewater treatment.

Adsorption isotherms :

Langmuir and Freundlich models of adsorption isotherms are most frequently used for determining the adsorption capacity and to delineate the adsorption mechanism. For adsorption isotherm studies, adsorbent dose was varied (ranging from 1 g L⁻¹ to 10 g L⁻¹), by keeping other parameters constant (C_i 51.8 g L⁻¹, temperature 25 °C ± 2 °C, shaking speed 150 rpm, initial pH = 7.6 and contact time 2 h). The Langmuir model is based on monolayer adsorption on uniform homogeneous surface with sites of identical nature. The Langmuir adsorption model can be represented in linear form as follows²¹ :

$$1/q_e = 1/q_{\max} b * 1/C_e + 1/q_{\max}$$

where, q_{\max} is the maximum amount of the fluoride ion per unit weight of adsorbent to form a complete monolayer on the surface, b is a constant related to the affinity of the binding sites. q_e represents equilibrium capacity. The values of Langmuir parameters, q_{\max} and b at room temperature were calculated from the slope and intercept of the linear plot of $1/q_e$ vs $1/C_e$ (Fig. 4).

Fig. 3. Effect of presence of co-existing ions on % fluoride removal on COCA.

Fig. 4. Langmuir adsorption isotherm for fluoride adsorption on COCA.

The Freundlich model indicates the heterogeneity of the adsorbent surface and considers multilayer adsorption. The linear form of Freundlich adsorption model is as follows²¹ :

$$\log q_e = \log K_F + 1/n \log (C_e)$$

where K_F and $1/n$ are Freundlich constants, related to adsorption capacity and adsorption intensity (heterogene-

ity factor) respectively. The values of K_F and $1/n$ were obtained from the slope and intercept of the linear Freundlich plot of $\log q_e$ vs $\log C_e$ (Fig. 5). The values of various adsorption isotherm parameters obtained from the two models are presented in Table 1. On comparison of the fitness of the two isotherm models it is evident that the experimental data were well fitted to Freundlich model

Fig. 5. Freundlich adsorption isotherm for fluoride adsorption on COCA.

Table 1. Various adsorption isotherm parameters for fluoride adsorption onto COCA

Model parameters	COCA
Langmuir isotherm	
q_{\max} (mg g ⁻¹)	15.75
K_L (mol L ⁻¹)	0.035
R^2	0.92
Freundlich isotherm	
K_f (mg g ⁻¹)	1.051
$1/n$	0.66
R^2	0.95

(R^2 : 0.95) as compared to Langmuir model (R^2 : 0.92) signifying the multilayer adsorption of fluoride on heterogeneous surface²².

Comparison with other adsorbents :

A comparison has been made between COCA and some previously reported adsorbents for fluoride removal in wastewater. COCA shows better fluoride adsorption properties than many other adsorbents²³⁻²⁵ in terms of pH, aluminium release, kinetics, selectivity and cost. Also, bare or unmodified granular activated Puralox Sasol alumina was evaluated for its defluoridation capacity in wastewater, which gave significantly less capacity of 2.3 mg g⁻¹. This further confirms that modification of alumina with copper oxide significantly enhances the fluoride uptake capacity as well as improvement with respect to

working range pH and interference due to competing ions.

Conclusions

From the experimental results of fluoride adsorption onto copper oxide impregnated alumina, the following inferences could be made :

(i) The adsorption capacity obtained at adsorbent dose of 4 g L⁻¹ was 7.3 mg g⁻¹ with initial F concentration of 51.8 mg L⁻¹ indicating its potential for the removal of fluoride from industrial wastewater, which in turn can reduce fluoride pollution from ground water.

(ii) pH was monitored before and after treatment with COCA. It was found that the initial pH of the solution containing only fluoride ions was 7.6 and the final pH after treatment was found to be in the range of 7.1 to 7.6. Whereas, the initial pH of simulated water containing other anions was 9.1, which remained unchanged even after treatment. This indicates that there is not much difference in pH, before and after treatment with COCA.

(iii) Comparative adsorption capacity was obtained even in presence of competing ions.

(iv) The batch adsorption studies revealed that the data obtained was well fitted in Freundlich model showing multilayer adsorption. The adsorption capacities obtained from the Langmuir and Freundlich models were 15.75 and 1.051 mg g⁻¹ respectively.

(v) Thus it is confirmed that the adsorption capacity of the activated alumina can be enhanced by modifying it with copper oxide, serving as a potential option for fluoride removal in wastewater.

Acknowledgement

This work was carried out under the CSIR sponsored project ESC-0108-MESER-402. Authors would like to thank JNARDDC for some of the characterization studies and Director, CSIR-NEERI for providing facilities.

References

1. <http://www.phadjustment.com/Fluoride/Fluoride-Removal-from-Industrial-Wastewater.html>.
2. A. K. Susheela, "A Treatise on Fluorosis, Fluorosis Research and Rural Development Foundation", New Delhi, India, 2003, revised 2nd ed.
3. Y. Zhou, C. Yu and Y. Shan, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2004, **36**, 89.
4. M. Islam and R. K. Patel, *Chem. Eng. J.*, 2011, **169**, 68.
5. <http://www.wastech.com/pages/hf-treatment-fluoride-removal>.
6. Alain Tressaud (ed.), "Advances in Fluorine Science, Fluorine and the Environment, Agrochemicals, Archaeology, Green Chemistry and Water", Elsevier, 2006, Vol. 2.
7. S. Ghorai and K. K. Pant, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2005, **42**, 265.
8. M. G. Sujana, R. S. Thakur and S. B. Rao, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 1998, **206**, 94.
9. C. J. Huang and J. C. Liu, *Water Res.*, 1999, **33**, 3403.
10. K. M. Popat, P. S. Anand and B. D. Dasare, *React. Polym.*, 1994, **23**, 23.
11. F. Luo and K. Inoue, *Solvent Extr. Ion Exch.*, 2004, **22**, 305.
12. I. B. Solangi, S. Memon and M. I. Bhangar, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **171**, 815.
13. S. Meenakshi and N. Viswanathan, *J. Colloid Interface Sci.*, 2007, **308**, 438.
14. N. Viswanathan and S. Meenakshi, *J. Hazard. Mater.*, 2009, **162**, 920.
15. R. Simons, *Desalination*, 1993, **89**, 325.
16. P. Sehn, *Desalination*, 2008, **223**, 73.
17. S. K. Adhikary, U. K. Tipnis, W. P. Harkare and K. P. Govindan, *Desalination*, 1989, **71**, 301.
18. S. Ayoob, A. K. Gupta and V. T. Bhat, *Crit. Rev. Environ. Sci. Technol.*, 2008, **38**, 401.
19. S. S. Tripathi, J. L. Bersillon and Krishna Gopal, *Sep. Purif. Technol.*, 2006, **50**, 310.
20. Bansiwala, P. Pillewan, R. B. Biniwale and S. S. Rayalu, *Microporous and Mesoporous Materials*, 2010, **129**, 54.
21. Y. S. Ho and G. McKay, *Process Biochem.*, 1999, **34**, 451.
22. W. J. Weber, "Physico-chemical Process for Water Quality Control", Wiley Interscience Publication, New York, 1972.
23. N. Hamdi and E. Srasra, *Desalination*, 2007, **206**, 238.
24. H. Kurosak, *Oki Technical Review*, 1998, Vol. **63**.
25. V. K. Gupta, Imran Ali and V. K. Saini, *Water Res.*, 2007, **41**, 3307.

